

OIL SUBSIDY REMOVAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: THE MITIGATING ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

For decades, Nigeria was one of the few nations that subsidized oil for its citizens. This practice, which ate into the nation's revenue, was sustained by subsequent governments as a means of mitigating the rising cost of living for her people, despite not prioritizing health and education subsidies. However, the current government, on assumption of office, declared the removal of the oil subsidy. This declaration heralded a corresponding rise in the price of oil, accompanied by food and commodity prices. On this note, this paper examined the role of the digital economy, measured by the volumes of POS and ATM transactions between 2022Q₁-2023Q₂, and after the removal of fuel subsidy in mitigating the impact on economic growth and employment around 2022Q₃-2024Q₄. The study utilized secondary datasets from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics. However, the role of the digital economy in mitigating the shocks from fuel subsidy removal was observed via the trends of POS and ATM volume of transactions relative to economic growth and employment. It was however established that the digital economy, before and particularly after the removal of fuel subsidy, promoted economic activities and created employment, in the aspect of facilitating quick transactions and informal sector workers who leveraged digital payment systems and sustain their operations.

Keywords: Oil Subsidy, Digital Economy, Growth, Employment, and Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Economic development remains a central policy focus in Nigeria, particularly in the face of recurring economic challenges such as unemployment, inflation, and income inequality. Economic development goes beyond mere increases in output, it further encompasses improvements in the standard of living, expansion of employment opportunities, and general welfare. Economic development, as defined by (Todaro & Smith, 2015) is a multidimensional process involving changes in national institutions, popular attitude, acceleration of growth, reduction in inequality and the eradication of poverty. Similarly, (Sen, 1999) defined economic

development as the expansion of human capabilities and freedoms, emphasizing access to basic services, productive employment, and improved quality of life.

Broadly, economic development is influenced by a range of factors, including human capital development, physical infrastructure, technological progress, and macroeconomic stability, all of which enhance productivity and improve the standards of living of the people, (Calderón & Servén, 2010; Rahman & Alam, 2021). On the whole, institutional quality and government policy play critical roles in influencing resource allocation and development.

As a national priority, past governments have pursued a range of policies to attract economic development with an intentional focus on employment generation, poverty reduction and general wellbeing. Such policies may include development programs with a focus on infrastructure, agriculture, like the National Poverty Eradication Program (NAPEP) 2001, the Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACCS) 2009, to offer low-interest financing to commercial farmers, with the aim of boosting productivity and food security, as well as the National Social Investment Program (NSIP) 2015, launched to fast track the conditional cash transfers, school feeding programs, and youth employment. Other notable policies are the monetary policy, whose prime objective is to stabilize internal prices, fiscal policy, with the objective to stimulate growth through revenue generation and spending.

Nonetheless, Nigeria's fiscal policy extends to the management of petroleum subsidies, which has been used to regulate domestic fuel prices to protect households against high energy costs. Accordingly, the (OECD, 2005) defines subsidy as "a measure that keeps prices for consumers below market levels or for producers above market levels, or that reduces costs for both consumers and producers" Similarly, International Monetary Fund describes subsidies as government interventions that alter market outcomes by providing financial support or preferential treatment to targeted groups (IMF, 2013).

However, to the International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2026) have argued that fossil subsidies such as fuel such subsidy are associated with substantial costs, such as higher government borrowing and taxes and, lower spending, inefficient-growth retarding allocation of resources, and pollution. Subsidies may also not be well targeted, thus benefiting the rich rather than the poor (IMF, 2026). The International Monetary Fund (2026) observed that the removal of subsidies and their redirection towards areas such as social spending and productive investment will promote equitable and sustainable outcomes, as well as reducing energy security fears caused by the volatile supply of fuel.

This above view has provided the basis for calls for the removal of fuel subsidies in countries all over the world. In Nigeria, the government has over the years cited the heavy-unsustainable fiscal burden imposed by the subsidy and the diversion of subsidized fuel to other countries as the reason for the removal of fuel subsidy in the country. According to the Nigeria Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (NEITI) Audit Report (2012), Nigeria spent over 4.8 trillion naira in the last seven years as subsidy on petroleum products imported into the country. Furthermore, a total of 1,355 trillion naira was processed for payment as subsidy. A breakdown revealed that 116,554 billion naira was paid from 2006 to 2008, 3 trillion naira from 2009 to 2011 and 690 billion naira in 2012. The subsidy regime, therefore, imposed severe financial burdens on the government, crowding out expenditure on critical sectors such as health, education, and infrastructure (World Bank, 2022). Arising from this, past administrations undertook a number of reforms, such as; the partial deregulation efforts in 2012 and the complete removal of fuel subsidy in 2023 with the goal to redirect resources toward productive investment.

Consequently, fuel subsidy removal has generated a number of challenges such as rising inflation, high cost of living, negative economic growth of -0.3% from 3.10% in 2022 to 2.74% in 2023, (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023), and potential adverse effects on employment and welfare, thereby necessitating complementary policies to mitigate its impact on economic

development. Given this trajectory, this study specifically addressed the following objectives: examine the role of digital economy in mitigating the impact of subsidy removal on economic growth in Nigeria, and; determine the role of digital economy in mitigating the impact of subsidy removal on unemployment in Nigeria.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Most of the recent studies on the effects of oil sector outcomes on economic development focus the effects of oil prices and changes in oil prices on economic development indices such as economic growth, human capital development, and poverty. With respect to Nigeria, these include the study by Edeh et al. (2017) which examined the impact of volatility in oil prices on human capital development and investment in Nigeria between the first quarter of 1981 and last quarter of 2013, through the use of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Exponential Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (EGARCH) model, found that oil price volatility has a negative and statistically significant impact on human capital development in Nigeria, and a positive and statistically significant impact on investment. A similar study by Okereke and Obinna (2022), carried out using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and data for the months, January 2010 to December 2021, found that the price of premium motor spirit has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria in the short and long-run, while the price of automotive gas oil and crude oil have a negative and insignificant impact in both the long and short-run.

Another study by Adamu and Usman (2022), carried out using data for the period 1989 to 20220 and the ARDL model found that oil prices have a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria in the short and long-run, while crude oil production has a positive but insignificant impact on economic growth in the long-run and a negative but insignificant impact in the short-run. Another study by Anakwue et al. (2024) examined the impact of oil price fluctuation on economic growth in Nigeria from a sectoral perspective through the use of the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and data for the period 1995 to 2024. The study found that oil price fluctuations have growing but modest impact on economic growth in Nigeria, and explain 2.36% of the variation in economic growth in Nigeria in the long-run. A similar study by Kavkav et al. (2025), carried out using the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) technique found that oil price has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Anue et al. (2017) examined the welfare and oil market impacts of oil consumption subsidy withdrawal from non-Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and, Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) by using a dynamic simulation model, and found that the effects of the withdrawal of the subsidies were significantly pronounced with significant declines in the consumption of oil in the transport sectors of the OPEC members and such countries being worse off by the withdrawal. The study however found that the overall welfare in the OPEC countries increased due to the higher profits derived from the production of oil.

Studies explicitly focusing on the effects of subsidy removal on economic development indicators include the study by Gamette and Oteng (2024) which reviewed the effects of the removal of fuel subsidies in the global south-oil producing economies between 2000 and 2023 by using the Arkesy and O'Malley framework and 27 studies. The study found that the removal of the subsidies had negative effects on poverty in countries through increases in the cost of transportation. The study also found that the removal of fuel subsidies also resulted in disputes between citizens and policy makers with the latter being accused of being corrupt.

In a related study, Eyam, Peter & Ebi (20220). Investigated the impact of fiscal autonomy on educational attainment of the states in Nigeria. The focus is on the 36 states in Nigeria and the

capability of a state to internally generate revenue as a basic requirement in the provision of social infrastructure and economic development. To investigate the relationship involving fiscal autonomy and educational attainment in Nigeria, instrumental variable three stage least squares (3SLS) panel estimation framework was adopted. The result from the rigorous estimation technique of 3SLS seem to give support to the hypothesis that increase in fiscal autonomy can significantly drive increase in literacy rate vis –a-vis educational attainment across the states and hence economic development in Nigeria. The study therefore strongly advocates that states should tow the middle path of being completely fiscal autonomous in striving for fiscal autonomy as fiscal autonomy can necessarily guarantee high educational attainment and economic development of states in Nigeria. More so, Shittu, Latiff and Baharudin (2024) assessed the reinvestment and compensation plans for fuel subsidy rationalization in Nigeria using the Dynamic Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model. The study found that the total one-off removal of fuel subsidy leads to severe economic headwinds and substantial loss of welfare.

Another study by Shittu, Latiff, Baharudin and Mohd (2024) investigated the economy-wide consequences of the targeting and repurposing of fuel subsidies in Malaysia using the Dynamic Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model. The study found that fuel subsidy removal has positive effects on the Malaysian economy in the medium and long-term, with the sequencing of the phaseout of subsidies, provision of compensation to vulnerable households, and reinvestment in health, food assistance, education and transportation ensuring the avoidance of the short-term adverse effects on output and households.

Okorie and Wesseh (2024) examined the relationship between the removal of fuel subsidy, economic welfare and the quality of the environment under different policy schemes in Nigeria through the use of the second version of the African Energy and Environment Integrated Computable General Equilibrium (AEEICGE) model. The study found that while subsidy removal enhances environmental quality, it also negatively affects the well-being of economic agents and raises the general price level. Such adverse effects were found to be reversed when the subsidy is differentially reallocated to households and business in the form of government transfer payments

Belgioioso and Newman (2025) examined the relationship between fossil fuel subsidy reform, distributive justice and civil unrest between 2015 and 2022. The study found that the reform on fossil fuel subsidy increases social unrest in countries lacking distributive justice. The study by Mokhtari and Ghoddusi (2025) found that the reduction of fuel subsidies with universal, direct and unconditional transfers would reduce the Gini coefficient of expenditure of Iran by 8% for every \$1 per capita reallocation. The study was carried out using data on Iranian household expenditure for the years 1984 to 2019.

Finally, Foo (2026) assessed the reforms on fuel subsidy in Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) countries between 2003 and 2022 using the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimator. The study found that the removal of fuel subsidy affects oil prices, gross domestic product and household consumption in both long and short-run in the ASEAN countries.

Extant studies on oil subsidy removal and economic development in Nigeria reveals a torrent of gaps that the study on the role of the digital economy, measured by the volumes of point of sales (POS) and automated teller machine (ATM) transactions, in mitigating the impact of fuel subsidy removal on economic development in Nigeria using data between the first quarter of 2022 and last quarter of 2024. Seeks to address. While prior studies examined the effect of oil prices and oil prices on economic development in Nigeria, none have examined addressed the subject matter of this study, particularly through the use of quarterly data.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The study employed the descriptive research design by presenting trends with a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative data. This design is suitable for understanding the role of the digital economy in mitigating the impact of subsidy removal on economic growth, and employment in Nigeria.

3.2 Theoretical framework

This paper is anchored on the Price Elasticity of Demand Theory, propounded by Professor Alfred Marshall in 1890. According to Marshall, the elasticity or responsiveness of demand in a market is considered high or low depending on whether the quantity demanded increases significantly or slightly following a decrease in price, and conversely, decreases significantly or slightly following a price increase. In essence, the price elasticity of demand is a statistical concept that measures the proportional change in the quantity demanded in response to changes in price and other influencing factors. Again, the theory explains the conditions under which a change in price either an increase or a decrease has varying effects on the quantity demanded. Despite criticisms from renowned American economist Professor Paul Samuelson, who dismissed the concept of elasticity as “essentially arbitrary,” “of no consequence,” and merely a “mental exercise for beginning students,” the theory remains highly relevant to this study. It serves as a useful tool for analyzing the socioeconomic and economic implications of policies such as fuel subsidy removal, especially in relation to poverty levels in Nigeria.

In this context, the elasticity of demand helps explain the paradox of poverty amid an abundance of petroleum products. The removal of fuel subsidies, which has led to an increase in the price of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS), has made the product more available in supply but less accessible in demand, as many consumers can no longer afford to purchase it in the quantities they previously did. Furthermore, the inflationary pressures triggered by subsidy removal may result in economic hardship rather than prosperity. While fuel availability has increased, the high costs of transportation and other essentials have reduced consumer purchasing power. As a result, producers may see reduced demand for their goods, leading to lower revenues despite ample supply. In such a scenario, poverty becomes not only widespread but inevitable.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Presentation of trends

In this study, the digital economy is measured through the use of transactions carried out through the use of point of sales (POS) and automated teller machine (ATM). Economic growth is measured using the growth rate of real gross domestic product.

The trend of POS and ATM transactions, used as proxies for the digital economy in Nigeria between 2022Q1 to 2023Q2 featuring the time before and during the early period of fuel subsidy removal, along with economic growth (GDPGR) trend during the same period is presented in figure 1. The data in the figure reveals that in the pre-subsidy removal times, POS transactions were volatile, giving that transaction volumes rose by 101% in first quarter of 2023, (Q1), possibly driven by the naira redesign policy that limited cash transactions, and equally boosted the use of

Fig.1 Trend analysis of the role of digital economy via point of sales (POS) and automated teller machine (ATM) transactions on economic growth before the removal of fuel subsidy between 2022Q1 to 2023Q2

Source: Computed by the researchers using quarterly data from the National Bureau of Statistics (2023) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Annual Statistical Bulletin (2023).

POS channels. On the other hand, ATM transactions were inconsistent, being that usage declined by -37.37% in 2023Q1 possibly due to reduced cash availability, but saw a recovery in 2022 quarter three, by about 17.38%. On the whole, economic growth witnessed stability within this period, dangling between 2.25% (2022Q3) and 3.54% (2022Q2), with a slight decline to 2.31% in 2023 quarter 1. Given this, it can be seen that the volume of transactions by POS agents saw progress before subsidy removal policy.

However, the 2023 quarter two which fell within the period of the subsidy removal saw a drop in the volume of POS transactions to 3.14%, pointing to a reduction in digital payment channels, as a response from rising fuel at the moment. Surprisingly, ATM transactions witnessed a 13.87% increase, indicating growing usage of digital channels, due to households and businesses adjustments to the subsidy shock. Notably, GDPGR rose to 2.51% from 2.31% in 2023Q1, indicating resilience, despite the pressure from the shocks. However, the recovery in ATM transactions as well as the slight rise in POS usage in 2023Q2 point to the digital economy’s role in mitigating the sufferings from the quagmires. Notably, the slight increase in the economy, as seen by the rise in GDPGR agrees with the hypothesis that digital tools played a role in curbing the effects of subsidy removal respectively.

Fig 2: Trend analysis of the role of digital economy via point of sales (POS) and automated teller machine (ATM) transactions on economic growth before the removal of fuel subsidy between 2023Q3 to 2024Q4.

Source: Computed by the researchers using quarterly data from the National Bureau of Statistics (2023) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Annual Statistical Bulletin (2023).

Figure 2 above show a trend of POS and ATM transactions used to proxy the digital economy in Nigeria between 2023Q3 to 2024Q4 reflecting the period after fuel subsidy removal, with respect to economic growth trend around the same period. However, in quarter 3 2023, available data show that POS transactions decline by -5.97%, likewise, ATM transactions to -83.33%, arising from the response to subsidy removal policy, and further revealing a reduction in consumer spending. In the midst of this, economic growth remained stable at 2.54%. On the whole, 2023Q4 saw a rise in POS transactions by 13.89%, while ATM transactions surge by circa 434.76%, this rebound in digital payment implied that businesses and households were swift to adjust to the changes, coinciding with a GDPGR increase to 3.46%, implying that the use of POS and ATM channels may have contributed to economic activity in the middle of price shocks.

However, as of 2024Q1, both POS and ATM transactions fell by -43.79% and -45.3%, possibly due to other factors like inflation, or unbalanced digital infrastructure availability, despite, economic growth stood at 2.98%, meaning that other economic factors like oil exports and tax revenue sustained growth. Moreso, from 2024 quarter two forward, POS usage grew by 0.73% in 2024Q2, 4.35% in Q3, and 17.7% in 2024 quarter four. On the other hand, ATM usage rose by 4.85% in 2024Q2, and 7.2% in 2024 quarter four. Most importantly, economic growth rose to 3.19% in 2024Q2 and settled at 3.6% in 2024Q4. The recovery in digital transactions shows that that the digital economy played a role in sustaining economic growth via effective financial transactions, by equally helping businesses and consumers adapt to higher costs, and maintaining growth stability.

Fig 3: Trend analysis of the role of digital economy via point of sales (POS) and automated teller machine (ATM) on unemployment rate before the removal of fuel subsidy between 2022Q1 to 2023Q2

Source: Computed by the researchers using quarterly data from the National Bureau of Statistics (2023) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Annual Statistical Bulletin (2023).

Figure 3 above show a trend of POS and ATM transactions as proxies for the digital economy in Nigeria between 2022Q1 to 2023Q2 capturing the time before and during the early period of fuel subsidy removal, as well as unemployment (UN) trend during the same period. However, available data show that in the pre-subsidy removal period, POS usage revealed growth, especially rising to 101% in the first quarters of 2023, possibly due to naira redesign policy which hoarded cash accessibility as well as boost POS usage. On the other hand, ATM transactions showed sustained volatility, with declines in 2022Q1 -3.43%, and 2022Q2 -6.18%, as well as a sharp drop in 2023Q1 of -37.37%, contrasted by a peak in 2022Q3 17.38%. Notably during this period, unemployment stayed stable, declining sluggishly from 5.5% in 2022Q1–2022Q2 to 5.3% in 2022Q4, and further dropped to 4.1% in 2023Q1. This means the expansion of POS outlets heralded job creation, conforming with the objective of examining the digital economy’s role in mitigating unemployment during the subsidy removal period.

However, the 2023Q2 saw a slowdown in POS transactions, coinciding with the early periods of fuel subsidy removal, reflecting potential economic difficulties from growing costs of fuel that likely reduced consumer spending. More so, ATM transactions, recovered to 13.87%, pointing to increased reliance on digital cash access as households and businesses adjusted to the subsidy shock. Notably, unemployment rate slightly increases to 4.2% from 4.1% in 2023Q1, pointing to a minor setback like higher transportation and production costs, possibly caused by subsidy removal. Interestingly, the low unemployment rate, alongside sustained transaction activity, particularly in ATM use, points to the digital economy’s role in maintaining economic stability. The continued use of digital payment systems likely supported small businesses and informal sector workers, who rely on POS and ATM infrastructure, thereby cushioning the unemployment impact during this period.

Figure 4 contains data on the trend of POS and ATM transactions used to proxy the digital economy in Nigeria between 2023Q3 to 2024Q4 capturing the period after the fuel subsidy removal, comparing with the unemployment (UN) trend during the same period. However, POS

transactions decline by -5.97%, likewise ATM transactions dropped -83.33%, likely arising from immediate economic shock of subsidy removal. Within this same period, unemployment rate rose to circa 5.0%, pointing to reduced labor demand due to rising operational costs. Notably, by 2023Q4, POS transactions recover to 13.89%, and ATM transactions skyrocketed by 434.76%, showing high rebound in digital channel usage. Similarly, the unemployment rate plummeted to 4.3%, implying that the digital economy’s resurgence may have supported job creation.

In the first quarter of 2024, both POS and ATM usage reduced by -43.79% and -45.3%, possibly due to

Fig 3: Trend analysis of the role of digital economy via point of sales (POS) and automated teller machine (ATM) on unemployment rate before the removal of fuel subsidy between 2023Q3 to 2024Q4.

Source: Computed by the researchers using quarterly data from the National Bureau of Statistics (2023) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Annual Statistical Bulletin (2023).

persistent inflation, or a dearth in digital infrastructure. The unemployment rate rose to 5.3%, likely fueled by job losses. On the whole, from 2024Q2 forward, POS transactions grew by circa 0.73%, 4.35%, and 17.7% between 2024Q2, 2024Q3, and 2024Q4. Meanwhile, ATM transactions in 2024Q2 rose by 4.85%, and 72.2% by 2024Q4. Conversely, unemployment rate fell to 4.3% in 2024Q2, 4.2% in 2024Q3, and 4.1% in 2024Q4. The downward trend in unemployment, accompanied by a rise in the volume of digital transaction, means that the digital economy, to some extent, promoted economic activity and created employment, in the aspect of enabling small businesses and informal sector workers who leveraged digital payment systems and sustain their operations.

4.2 Discussion of findings

The trends in POS and ATM transactions, as proxies for Nigeria’s digital economy, across the pre-subsidy and post-subsidy removal periods shows their collective role in mitigating the impact of fuel subsidy removal on economic development, particularly in the aspect of growth and employment generation. However, in the Pre-subsidy removal period, the notable surge in POS transactions of about 101% growth in 2023Q1 was said to be driven by the naira redesign policy, while ATM transactions were volatile, with a sharp decline (-37.37%) in 2023Q1. GDP growth rate (GDPGR) remained stable, ranging from 2.25% to 3.54%, and slightly increased to 2.51% in 2023Q2 despite subsidy removal’s onset. Post-subsidy, despite initial declines, digital transactions rebounded strongly in 2023Q4 and

stabilized in 2024, with GDPGR peaking at 3.6% in 2024Q4. Notably, these findings implies that the digital economy, through sustained POS and ATM activity, facilitated transactional efficiency and commerce, helping to curb economic shocks from subsidy removal. The stable and rising economic growth, particularly in 2023Q4 and 2024Q4, indicates that digital financial tools like POS and ATM usage supported economic resilience after the implementation of fuel subsidy removal.

On the other hand, POS and ATM's role in fighting unemployment impacts is evident in the unemployment rate trends. However, before subsidy removal, unemployment declined from 5.5% in 2022Q1 to 4.1% in 2023Q1, coinciding with rising POS growth, implying that digital transactions heralded job creation in retail and fintech. Behold, in 2023Q2, unemployment rose slightly to 4.2% as POS usage slowed by 3.14%, reflecting subsidy removal's impact. After the removal, unemployment stood at 5.3% in 2024Q1 in the midst of a reduction in digital transactions but steadily declined to 4.1% by 2024Q4, aligned with rising POS and ATM usage by 17.7%, and 72.2%. This indicates that the digital economy helped stabilize employment despite subsidy-induced cost pressures.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The thrust of this paper was to examine the role of oil subsidy removal in economic development in Nigeria, as well as reviewing the mitigating role of POS and ATM machines before and after the subsidy removal policy. However, results from the trends revealed that despite the digital economy's role in mitigating the effects of subsidy removal on Nigeria's employment rate as well as economic growth, it was faced with structural and economic barriers like insufficient ATM machines in some crude parts of the country, and very low level of awareness of the use of POS machines. Despite this challenges, the results revealed that digital financial tools, particularly POS and ATM systems, were important for economic resilience during, and after the shocks from the fuel subsidy removal. The following recommendation are presented from the results of the trends;

- I. The study recommends that government expand digital infrastructure, particularly via increasing internet availability and POS terminal accessible in rural, and inaccessible areas.
- II. Government should equally promote digital awareness programs to enhance the usage among small businesses in Nigeria.
- III. Finally, policy makers should implement policies to stabilize consumer spending as well as promote digital transaction growth.

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APPENDIX

YEAR	POS	ATM	GDPGR	UNP
2022Q1	6.7	-3.43	3.11	5.5
2022Q2	-1.88	-6.18	3.54	5.50
2022Q3	16.2	17.38	2.25	5.4
2022Q4	21.3	-4.36	3.52	5.3
2023Q1	101	-37.37	2.31	4.1
2023Q2	3.14	13.87	2.51	4.2
YEAR	POS	ATM	GDPGR	UNP
2023Q3	-5.97	-83.33	2.54	5
2023Q4	13.89	434.76	3.46	4.3
2024Q1	-43.79	-45.3	2.98	5.3
2024Q2	0.73	4.85	3.19	4.3
2024Q3	4.35	-42.83	3.46	4.2
2024Q4	17.7	72.2	3.6	4.1
Overall (2022Q1– 2024Q4)	113.51	-62.18		

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2023; National Bureau of Statistics Publications, 2024.